

Electrometric Studies on Thallium (I) Thio-Molybdate

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The formation and composition of Thallous-thio-molybdate obtained by the interaction of $TlNO_3$ and Na_2MoS_4 have been investigated by means of electrometric techniques involving amperometric, pH -metric, E.M.F. and conductometric titrations between the reactants at several concentrations. The results obtained provide definite evidence for the formation of Thallous thio-molybdate at pH range 7.0—8.0. The precipitation of this compound has been found to be almost quantitative and the accuracy and reproducibility of amperometric titrations are of a high order.

A survey of literature reveals that there are very few references to the study of thiomolybdates of metals, specially those of the less common elements, and most workers had based their conclusions on the analytical investigations only. There is, however, no reference available on the study of thio-molybdate of Thallium (I). Hence the present investigation has been initiated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anala.R. (BDH) reagents, thallous nitrate, potassium nitrate, molybdic acid, sodium sulphide, ammonium sulphide, and gelatin were used and their solutions prepared in air-free conductivity water. The solution of sodium thio-molybdate was prepared by digesting analysed sample of molybdenum tri-sulphide in sodium sulphide solution of required strength.

A manual polarograph with scalamp galvanometer was employed for amperometric titrations. A series of polarograms of solutions containing different concentrations of $TlNO_3$ in presence of 0.1M KNO_3 and 0.01% gelatin were drawn and the potential at which a limiting current plateau is reached, was determined, which was found to be -0.7 v (vs. SCE). Amperometric titrations were carried out at $E_{d.e.} = -0.7v$. using 0.1M KNO_3 as supporting electrolyte and 0.01% gelatin, as maximum suppressor. Twenty ml of the titre solution was taken in the cell each time, which was swept and stirred by bubbling purified hydrogen. The end-points were located graphically by plotting corrected current values as a function of ml of titrant added.

pH and E.M.F. measurements were carried out on Cambridge null deflection type pH meter using a wide range glass electrode and a bright platinum foil as an indicator electrode in conjunction with S.C.E. Twenty five ml of titre solution was taken in the cell each time. The end-points were obtained from the sharp inflections in titration curves and confirmed further from the maxima in dpH/dV and dE/dV .

The conductance measurements were performed on an electronic-eye indicator type conductometer. Twenty five ml of solution was taken in the conductivity cell each time and

thermostated at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The conductance values after correcting for dilution effect were plotted as a function of ml of titrant added and the end-points were judged from the breaks in titration curves.

Using different concentrations of reactants a series of amperometric, glass electrode, e.m.f. and conductometric titrations were carried out both by direct and reverse methods (i.e. when $TlNO_3$ solution from microburette was added to Na_2MoS_4 solution and vice-versa). The same strengths of solutions were employed in all the techniques for the sake of comparison of results. Amperometric, pH , e.m.f., and conductometric titration results have been summarised in table-I. Four figures illustrating direct and reverse amperometric (Fig. 1), pH (Fig. 2), e.m.f. (Fig. 3) and conductometric (Fig. 4) titrations curves have been given.

FIG 1 ml of titrant

CURVE I - M/10 $TlNO_3$ ADDED TO 20 ml OF M/120 Na_2MoS_4
 CURVE II - M/20 $TlNO_3$ ADDED TO 20 ml OF M/300 Na_2MoS_4
 CURVE III - M/20 Na_2MoS_4 ADDED TO 20 ml OF M/100 $TlNO_3$
 CURVE IV - M/50 Na_2MoS_4 ADDED TO 20 ml OF M/200 $TlNO_3$

FIG 2

CURVE I - M/10 $TlNO_3$ ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/120 Na_2MoS_4
 CURVE II - M/20 $TlNO_3$ ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/300 Na_2MoS_4
 CURVE III - M/10 Na_2MoS_4 ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/100 $TlNO_3$
 CURVE IV - M/50 Na_2MoS_4 ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/200 $TlNO_3$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Amperometric titrations between $TlNO_3$ and Na_2MoS_4 solutions were carried out at an applied potential of -0.7v. (vs. SCE). In direct titrations (fig. 1, curves—I & II) when thio-molybdate is used as titre, it is observed that MoS_4^{2-} ions do not yield any measurable diffusion current and no change in the value of current is noted on the addition of $Tl(NO_3)$ until the equivalence point ($Tl^+ : MoS_4^{2-} :: 2 : 1$) is reached, after which the diffusion current increases linearly with the addition of Tl^+ ions. In the case of inverse titrations (fig. 1, curves—III & IV,) the addition of Na_2MoS_4 solution to $TlNO_3$ solution the diffusion current produced by Tl^+ ions decreases gradually as a result of their removal as Tl_2MoS_4 and reach a minimum at the point where the reacting ratio of $Tl^+ : MoS_4^{2-}$ is 2 : 1 beyond which the

current remains almost constant. Amperometric titration curves are regular in shape and the accuracy and reproducibility of these titrations have been found to be excellent.

FIG 3

CURVE I - M/10 TiNO_3 ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/120 Na_2MoS_4

CURVE II - M/10 TiNO_3 ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/300 Na_2MoS_4

CURVE III - M/20 Na_2MoS_4 ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/100 TiNO_3

CURVE IV - M/160 Na_2MoS_4 ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/500 TiNO_3

FIG 4

CURVE I - M/10 TiNO_3 ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/120 Na_2MoS_4

CURVE II - M/20 TiNO_3 ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/300 Na_2MoS_4

CURVE III - M/20 Na_2MoS_4 ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/100 TiNO_3

CURVE IV - M/160 Na_2MoS_4 ADDED TO 25 ml OF M/500 TiNO_3

Fig. 2 shows the changes occurring in H^+ ion concentration during the reaction between thalious nitrate and sodium thio-molybdate. In direct titrations (fig. 2, curves—I & II) when thalious nitrate solution was added to (Na_2MoS_4) solution a gradual decrease in pH was observed till the stoichiometric end-point (where the molecular ratio of $Tl^+ : MoS_4^{2-} : 2 : 1$) is reached after which the smallest addition of titrant causes a sharp fall in pH indicating the completion of reaction and suggesting the formation of thalious thio-molybdate at the pH range 7.0—8.0. In the case of reverse titrations (curves—III & IV), an initial decrease in pH is observed on the addition of (Na_2MoS_4) and at the end point a marked jump in pH was noted confirming the formation of Tl_2MoS_4 according to the following equation:

A survey of the results of potentiometric titrations (Fig. 3) reveals that the reaction between $TlNO_3$ and Na_2MoS_4 can be suitably investigated by using a bright platinum foil as an indicator electrode. In direct titrations (curves—I & II), on the addition of $TlNO_3$ the e.m.f. remains almost constant until in the vicinity of end-point a sharp fall in potential is obtained, after which the e.m.f. remains practically unchanged. In reverse titrations (curves—III & IV), the e.m.f. changes gradually on addition of (Na_2MoS_4) and a steeper rise in potential is noted at a point corresponding to the reacting ratio of $Tl^+ : MoS_4^{2-}$ is 2 : 1 indicating the formation of Tl_2MoS_4 . Further addition of the reagent does not show any appreciable change in observed e.m.f.

TABLE I

Summary of results of Amperometric, pH, E.M.F. and Conductometric titrations

Molarity of solutions.		Equivalence points (ml) for the formation of Tl_2MoS_4					
$TlNO_3$	Na_2MoS_4	Amperometric (Vol. of titre 20 ml)		Calc.	pH	Observed. E.M.F.	Cond. (Vol. of titre 25 ml)
		Calc.	Obs.				
Direct titrations (Fig. 1, 2, 3 & 4, curves I & II)							
M/10	M/120	3.33	3.35	4.17	4.15	4.15	4.15
M/20	M/300	2.66	2.65	3.33	3.35	3.35	3.25
M/30	M/600	2.0	2.05	2.50	2.4	2.4	2.4
M/50	M/900	2.22	2.05	—	—	—	—
Reverse titrations (Fig. 1, 2, 3 & 4, curves III & IV).							
M/100	M/20	2.00	2.00	2.5	2.5	2.55	2.5
M/200	M/50	2.5	2.55	3.12	3.15	3.15	3.2
M/500	M/200	4.0	4.10	—	—	—	—
M/500	M/160	—	—	4.0	4.10	4.05	4.0
M/1000	M/500	5.0	5.10	—	—	—	—

Conductometric titration curves (Fig. 4) are regular in shape and show well defined breaks at the equivalence points corresponding to the formation of Tl_2MoS_4 .

It is noted that current, pH , e.m.f. and conductance values take a little time for attaining steady state. Every titration takes about half an hour for completion. The presence of ethanol has little effect on the precipitation of Tl_2MoS_4 ; its presence, however, slightly improves the position of the end-points as a consequence of the decrease in the solubility of Tl_2MoS_4 .

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